

Angelo Leogrande^{1*}°

*LUM University Giuseppe Degennaro, Casamassima, Bari, Puglia, Italy, EU

°LUM Enterprise s.r.l., Casamassima, Bari, Puglia, Italy, EU

The percentage of high-tech imports relative to total trade globally

Decreased by -6.2% between 2013 and 2022.

This variable represents the importance of imports of technological products and services within the overall international trade context of a nation. High-tech goods include products such as electronic components, computers, telecommunications equipment, biotechnology, advanced pharmaceuticals, medical devices, and other goods that require a high level of knowledge and research to be developed. The indicator is particularly relevant in the context of global innovation as it reflects a country's level of access to advanced technologies from other nations. A high percentage of high-tech imports may suggest that a country recognizes the need to integrate external technological solutions to stimulate internal innovation, improve productivity, and remain competitive. At the same time, excessive reliance on technological imports could indicate a limited capacity to develop such technologies domestically. From the perspective of the Global Innovation Index (GII), which assesses the innovative capabilities of countries globally, this variable helps to provide insight into the dynamics of a country's innovation ecosystem. Countries with more open and integrated economies tend to have a high percentage of high-tech imports in their total trade, as they rely on advanced technologies developed abroad to support their industrial and innovative processes. In summary, the variable "High-tech imports, % total trade" offers a snapshot of the role of advanced technologies in trade and provides useful insights into a country's ability to access and leverage global innovative solutions, which is crucial for economic and technological progress. The analyzed data refers to the period between 2013 and 2022.

The percentage of high-tech imports relative to total trade in 2022. The analysis of the data on advanced technology imports as a percentage of total trade for various countries in 2022 reveals an interesting overview of global economic and trade dynamics. The diversity of the results shows how countries significantly differ in the extent to which they rely on imports of advanced technological goods and services for their economic development. At the top of the rankings are Hong Kong SAR and Vietnam, both with a percentage of 100%. This result highlights how these economies are strongly oriented toward acquiring advanced technology from abroad. Hong Kong, as a global financial and commercial hub, uses its strategic position to import advanced technologies, thereby fostering innovation and economic development. Similarly, Vietnam has seen significant expansion in the manufacturing and technology sectors, benefiting from foreign investment and access to cutting-edge technologies through imports. The cases of the Philippines (97.6%) and Malaysia (93.4%) reveal a strong dependence on high-tech imports. These countries, located in the heart of Southeast Asia, have economies heavily reliant on the production of electronic components and technological products. High-tech imports therefore represent a crucial part of their supply chains, necessary to support industrial production and the export of finished products. With 85% of its imports represented by advanced technologies, China demonstrates its position as a global player in the technology sector. Despite being one of the leading producers and exporters of technology, China

¹Assistant Professor of Economics at LUM University Giuseppe Degennaro and Researcher at LUM Enterprise s.r.l. Email: leogrande.cultore@lum.it, Strada Statale 100 km 18, Casamassima, Bari, Puglia, Italia.

continues to significantly rely on imports of advanced technological components, especially for the production of complex goods such as microchips, semiconductors, and other key technologies. This dynamic reflects China's strategy of combining domestic production capacity with access to the best technologies available on the global market. Countries like Singapore (78.4%), South Korea (56.5%), and Thailand (56.5%) show how Asia as a whole is a key region for advanced technology trade. Singapore, with its economy strongly based on advanced services and high technology, continues to maintain a strong connection with high-tech imports, necessary to maintain its competitive position. South Korea, despite being one of the leading nations in the technology sector, shows a high percentage, indicating the importance of imports in completing the domestic production cycle, especially in sectors such as consumer electronics. The analysis of European and American countries reveals a different picture. The United States (59.3%), despite being a technological powerhouse, shows a relatively moderate level of high-tech imports relative to its total trade. This may reflect a robust and diversified domestic production capacity, although there remains a dependence on certain strategic goods and components from abroad. European countries such as the Czech Republic (74.3%) and Hungary (47.7%) show high percentages, highlighting the role they play as production centers for many multinational companies that take advantage of access to advanced imported technologies to fuel local production. Germany (29.7%), despite being a global leader in technological innovation, shows a lower percentage than the European average, reflecting the fact that much of the technology used in its industries is produced domestically. Countries like the United Kingdom (31.3%), France (28.5%), and Italy (23.6%) show moderate integration of high-tech imports, supported by mature economies with significant innovation capacities. However, access to imported advanced components and technologies remains crucial to sustaining the competitiveness of their industries. Observing emerging economies such as Brazil (39.1%), Mexico (60.2%), and India (30.6%), a significant dependence on technological imports is evident. These countries are working to strengthen their technological capabilities but currently have to rely on imports to support key sectors such as automotive, electronics, and ICT (Information and Communication Technology). In Africa and Central Asia, reliance on high-tech imports is generally low. Countries like Niger (64.8%), which show a high percentage, reflect cases where a developing economy disproportionately relies on a small number of imported goods to meet technological needs. However, most African countries like Angola (6%) and Ghana (4.2%) show low percentages, indicating a limited capacity to access advanced technologies, often due to economic and infrastructural constraints. Some developed countries like Norway (21.9%), Sweden (23.5%), and Switzerland (14.5%) show surprisingly low percentages. This reflects highly innovative economies with a strong capacity to produce the technologies they need domestically. However, even these nations rely on strategic imports to integrate their production chains, especially in highly specialized sectors. In summary, the data clearly shows how global economic innovation and competitiveness are strongly influenced by access to imported advanced technologies. Countries with a high percentage of high-tech imports often leverage these resources to stimulate economic growth, support industrial production, and maintain a competitive advantage. Conversely, nations with low percentages may struggle to compete in the global context, especially if they cannot develop or access the necessary technologies. These data also highlight the growing interconnectedness between countries, where imports of advanced technologies are not just a matter of access but of integration into global value chains. A country's ability to import advanced technology is, in many cases, a key indicator of its role in the global economy and its ability to innovate and grow in an increasingly technological and competitive environment.

The percentage of high-tech imports relative to total trade between 2013 and 2022. The analysis of the data on the percentage of advanced technology imports relative to total trade for various countries between 2013 and 2022 reveals significant changes in terms of growth or decline in these imports. This evolution is influenced by economic, geopolitical, and technological factors that vary greatly from country to country. In this context, it is interesting to examine the growth and decline trends of

these imports to better understand the dynamics driving the adoption and access to advanced technologies in different regions of the world. Among the countries with the largest percentage increases are Senegal (+731.58%), Zimbabwe (+247.95%), and Belarus (+231.25%). These countries, which historically had limited access to advanced technologies, have shown rapid growth in importing these goods. In the case of Senegal and Zimbabwe, this increase may be linked to development policies aimed at bridging the technology gap, facilitating the acquisition of foreign technologies to stimulate economic growth and improve efficiency in productive sectors. In Africa, Ethiopia (+158.77%) and Niger (+195.89%) are other examples of countries investing in advanced technologies with the aim of modernizing their economies. This growth can be attributed to foreign investments and international cooperation programs aimed at developing infrastructure and key sectors such as agriculture, health, and energy. In Asia, Vietnam (+135.85%) has seen exponential growth in advanced technology imports, reflecting its transformation into one of the world's leading manufacturing destinations. The country has become a technological production hub, attracting multinational companies that require imported high-tech components to support their local production. Vietnam's success highlights the key role of government policies focused on industrialization and integration into global value chains. Some countries, while registering growth, have seen a less pronounced increase in advanced technology imports. Among them are India (+61.9%), Moldova (+61.59%), and Pakistan (+120.5%). India, despite having a robust technology industry, continues to import advanced technologies to integrate its production capacities, especially in sectors such as defense, telecommunications, and energy. Pakistan, with an increase of 120.5%, reflects a growing need for advanced technologies to support strategic sectors such as energy and infrastructure. On the other hand, many countries have seen a significant reduction in the percentage of high-tech imports. Among these are Panama (-76.33%), Malta (-74.38%), and Ireland (-75.79%). The sharp decline in these countries may be attributed to structural changes in their economies or a greater ability to produce advanced technologies domestically. For example, Ireland has seen a 75.79% reduction in the percentage of high-tech imports, likely due to an increase in domestic production of technological goods, thanks to the presence of numerous multinationals that have established manufacturing plants in the country. The case of Switzerland (-70.88%) is particularly interesting. Despite being one of the most innovative countries in the world, Switzerland has drastically reduced its imports of advanced technologies. This could indicate a growing self-sufficiency in the production of cutting-edge technologies or a change in trade dynamics due to geopolitical factors or new trade policies. China and the United States, two of the largest economies in the world, show different trends. China, despite being a major exporter of advanced technologies, has seen a moderate increase (+9.25%) in its high-tech imports, highlighting its continued reliance on key imported components such as semiconductors, despite massive investments in domestic production. This figure reflects the Chinese paradox, where technological self-sufficiency is a strategic priority, but there is still strong dependence on foreign sources in crucial sectors. The United States, on the other hand, recorded a modest increase of 7.04%, a sign that despite its robust internal technology ecosystem, it continues to rely on specific imports, especially in areas such as advanced electronics and medical devices. This moderate increase can also be read in the context of growing trade tensions between the United States and China, which may have pushed the United States to diversify its sources of imports. Some countries have maintained relative stability in their imports of advanced technologies, with minimal variations. For example, Ecuador (+2.52%) and Slovakia (+4.93%) have not seen significant changes, which could indicate a stabilization of their economic model or a gradual transition to domestic production of certain technologies. Conversely, countries like Japan (-3.63%), Russia (-11.54%), and South Korea (+5.02%) show minimal variations, suggesting mature economies with a consolidated capacity to produce advanced technologies, thereby reducing the need for imports. Many developed countries have seen a significant decline, indicating a reduction in dependence on imports of advanced technologies. Sweden (-48.8%), Germany (-32.35%), and France (-36.53%) are notable examples of advanced economies that are reducing technology imports, likely thanks to an increase in domestic production. In Europe, this trend may be

linked to industrial strategies aimed at developing domestic capacities and strengthening economic resilience in an increasingly uncertain geopolitical context. In summary, the data analysis shows a clear division between countries that are rapidly increasing their imports of advanced technologies and those that are reducing their dependence on them. Emerging and developing countries are accelerating the adoption of advanced technologies through imports, a sign of their growing integration into global value chains. Conversely, many advanced economies are reducing these imports, indicating greater self-sufficiency or a change in trade dynamics. Moreover, the geopolitical context and trade tensions play a key role in determining these dynamics. Countries like China and the United States are trying to balance the need for imports with the aspiration for technological self-sufficiency. The evolution of these trends will be crucial in understanding how future global economic relations and the distribution of technology worldwide will take shape.

Economic Policies. Increasing the percentage of high-tech imports relative to total trade is a goal that requires a coordinated set of economic and strategic policies by governments. One of the first measures a government can adopt is the reduction of tariffs on imports of high-tech goods. Reducing or eliminating tariffs on advanced technological products facilitates the acquisition of these technologies, making them more accessible and competitive compared to local alternatives. Simplifying customs procedures and speeding up the clearance processes through the adoption of digital and automated systems can further facilitate the import of advanced technologies. Signing free trade agreements or preferential trade agreements with leading countries in the technology sector can boost high-tech imports. These agreements may include fiscal and tariff benefits for importing specific high-tech products, making it more convenient to purchase such goods from foreign countries. The creation of special economic zones with favorable fiscal and commercial regimes for companies operating in the technology sector can serve as an additional incentive. Attracting foreign direct investment (FDI) in the technology sector is crucial to increasing high-tech imports. Multinational companies investing in a country tend to bring advanced technologies to support their activities. Creating a favorable environment for FDI through tax incentives, subsidies, and a stable and transparent regulatory framework can encourage the presence of tech companies that import equipment, components, and high-level know-how. Small and medium-sized enterprises (SMEs) often lack the financial resources needed to invest in advanced technologies. Offering subsidized financing, low-interest loans, or targeted grants to businesses that import advanced technological goods can facilitate the acquisition of such technologies. Additionally, promoting public-private cooperation in financing technological projects can expand access to financial resources for importing high-tech goods. Efficient logistics are essential to facilitate the import of advanced technologies. Investing in modern infrastructure such as ports, airports, and transportation systems reduces import costs and accelerates the procurement of technologies from abroad. Digital infrastructure, such as supply chain management systems based on advanced technologies (blockchain, artificial intelligence), can help improve the efficiency and transparency of the import process. Increased imports of advanced technologies also require the presence of a qualified workforce capable of using them effectively. Investing in training and technical skills development programs, particularly in emerging technological sectors like artificial intelligence, robotics, biotechnology, and digitalization, is crucial for fully leveraging imported technologies. Collaborations between educational institutions and businesses can create study pathways aimed at developing the skills needed to manage imported advanced technologies. Targeted industrial policies can promote the import of advanced technologies by identifying strategic sectors for the national economy. Supporting the expansion of local tech industries that require advanced technologies, such as automation, ICT, and advanced manufacturing, can generate growing demand for imported tech goods. Moreover, industrial policies that promote collaboration between the public sector, private sector, and research institutes can accelerate the adoption of cutting-edge technologies. Promoting the adoption of advanced digital technologies within companies can stimulate the demand for imported technologies. Government initiatives that encourage digital transformation and the adoption of innovative practices through specific funds and

programs can increase the import of technological tools and components. Additionally, the creation of innovation ecosystems, such as technology parks or research hubs, can attract imports of advanced technologies necessary for experimental and development projects. Complex and restrictive regulations can be a significant barrier to importing advanced technologies. Reducing regulatory barriers, simplifying approval procedures, and aligning technical regulations with international standards can facilitate the import of technological products. A favorable and predictable regulatory environment is essential to attract economic operators willing to invest in advanced technologies from abroad. International cooperation in research and development can stimulate imports of advanced technologies through the sharing of knowledge and resources. Participating in international R&D programs and technology consortia can facilitate access to innovative technologies developed abroad, thus promoting the import of high-tech goods. Initiatives such as the creation of joint laboratories or participation in research projects sponsored by the EU or other international organizations can strengthen the capacity to import and use advanced technologies. Promoting the birth and growth of innovative start-ups can increase the demand for imported advanced technologies. Tech start-ups often require advanced tools and equipment to develop new products or services. Incubation, acceleration, and targeted financing programs for innovative companies can incentivize the import of advanced technologies, thus increasing the percentage of such imports in total trade. Increasing the "percentage of advanced technology imports relative to total trade" requires a comprehensive strategy that combines regulatory measures, economic incentives, and investments in human capital. By adopting an integrated approach that considers both the needs of the private sector and national development priorities, it is possible to create an environment conducive to the adoption of advanced technologies, thereby strengthening the competitiveness and innovation of the economy in the long term. Policies focused on trade openness, international cooperation, and skills development represent the fundamental pillars to achieving this objective.

Conclusions. The value of high-tech imports as a percentage of total trade decreased from 30.56 to 28.63, representing a reduction of -6.2%, equivalent to a decline of -1.92 units. There are countries where the percentage of high-tech imports relative to total trade increased significantly above the average, such as in the cases of Senegal with +731.58%, Zimbabwe with +247.95%, Belarus with +231.25%, Montenegro with +211.69%, Niger with +195.89%, and Nigeria with +159.43%. On the other hand, there are countries where this value decreased significantly, such as Switzerland with -70.88%, Malta with -74.38%, Ireland with -75.79%, Panama with -76.33%, and Ghana with -85.16%.

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